

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the concept and essence of educational innovations, provides a definition of innovations in the educational process. The authors of this article conducted a survey of students in grades 9-11 of secondary school No. 11, the purpose of which was to determine the knowledge of students about educational innovations and their readiness to learn using educational innovations. The sample consisted of 53 people. The results of this questionnaire indicate the following: in general, students adequately understand the essence of educational innovations, realize their importance in ensuring the quality of professional education; most students prefer a traditional form of education; more than half of the students are interested in modern educational technologies.

Keywords: innovations, education, active forms of education, electronic technologies.

Modern realities put forward their own requirements for today's youth - a student with developed critical thinking, ready to perceive the surrounding world in all its complexity, striving through self-realization to transform reality. A 21st century graduate must be proficient in foreign language for effectively solving communication problems in situations of personal communication and in conditions of academic mobility, when many students take part in international educational programs, communication situations in the educational environment. In the context of the need to improve the adaptation of high school students to work, earlier initial vocational training, the main goal of teaching a foreign language at school is the formation of foreign language communicative competence [1, p.45].

Unfortunately, among the set of modern methods of teaching foreign languages, it is not always easy for a teacher to select those teaching methods, which most effectively contribute to the formation of communicative competence. The content of education, focused on anticipating the development of society and personal development, presupposes the continuity of general and professional education at the

level of such component as a personal communication experience, including in a foreign language. We are interested in ways of organizing training that contribute to the awareness of the value of education in modern conditions and the need and willingness to learn constantly.

In other words, methods that transform learning foreign languages in the sphere of strategic development of the individual, help the formation of educational needs that initiate the pursuit of lifelong education. In modern conditions, one of the main criteria for the competitive advantage of an educational institution is the presence and successful implementation of various innovative forms and methods of teaching disciplines. Today, the topic of innovation in schools is raised at the state level. She is given special importance. The modern school is always in search of various ways to implement its own functions, one of which is innovation. Innovation should be understood as change, innovation, innovation.

It is worth noting that, historically, in one way or another, novelty is considered a relative concept. It has a concrete historical character, in other words, it may appear before "it's time", after which it turns into a normal phenomenon or becomes obsolete. From this we can conclude that the implementation of innovative activities in the school is continuous: some of its directions are constantly being replaced by others.

Innovation in education is understood as the process and results of targeted effective changes based on innovations that ensure a qualitative renewal and development of individual components and the entire system of vocational education [4, p.221]. Innovations can be the result of applied and fundamental research, experimental and theoretical developments in the field of vocational education, training, management and technology, which, when mastered, lead to the effectiveness and development of vocational education in the education system. Innovations in education are aimed at improving the quality of the vocational training process, increasing its organizational and economic efficiency. This leads to the need for purposeful management of the process of development and implementation of educational innovations in the activities of educational organizations, collection and systematization of information about them, the use of existing innovations in the promotion of educational services in secondary education.

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